

THE IMPORTANCE OF IDIOMS IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR LEARNERS

Qoraqo'ziyeva Diyora Iqboliddin qizi

Second-Year-Student of Master's Degree, Andijan State Institute of
Foreign Languages

***Abstract:** This article is devoted to the study of idioms which discusses specific features of phraseologies. In addition, it gives information about approaches to the classification of phraseological units and the importance of idioms in teaching English for learners.*

***Keywords:** phraseology, idiom, set expression, lexical meaning, figurative meaning, teaching idioms.*

Phraseology captures the vast experience of the people, reflects the ideas associated with the labor, life and cultural life of people. Phraseology is an important and integral part of any language. Over time, it accumulates phraseological units that allow us to look into the past of the people or to know the culture of another country, since phraseological units describe the mentality, national character, lifestyle, as a rule, and much more. It should be noted that the study of phraseology as an independent science has been conducted for a long time by both foreign and Russian scientists, but the interest in this field of linguistics has not faded to this day. Semantic characteristics and features of phraseological units are the focus of works by P. Kühn, H. Burger, V.V. Vinogradov, N.M. Shanskii and many others. The development of this problematic seems promising for identifying the national and cultural characteristics of English phraseological units, which allows us to increase our vocabulary and, therefore, enrich our speech.[1]

English is rich in idioms. They make a language sound, creative, and can also get others to think and figure out what the person might mean by using the idiom and it creates curiosity among the interlocutors to learn idioms. Idioms exist in all

languages and enjoy widespread use among speakers of every language the world over. According to the Cambridge Dictionary of English (2020), an idiom is "a group of words in a fixed order that have a particular meaning that is different from the meanings of each word on its own". According to Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2020), an idiom is "an expression in the usage of a language that is peculiar to itself either in having a meaning that cannot be derived from the conjoined meanings of its elements (such as up in the air for "undecided") or in its grammatically atypical use of words". A definition found in the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (2009) states that an idiom is "a group of words that has a special meaning that is different from the ordinary meaning of each separate word". For example, "under the weather" is an idiom meaning "ill" (p.870). An idiom according to World Book Dictionary (2001, p.1049) is "a phrase or expression whose meaning cannot be understood from the ordinary meanings of the words in it".

A.V. Koonin classified phraseological units according to the way they are formed. He pointed out primary and secondary ways of forming phraseological units. Primary ways of forming phraseological units are those when a unit is formed on the basis of a free word-group:

- a) The most productive in Modern English is the formation of phraseological units by means of transferring the meaning of terminological word-groups, e.g. in cosmic technique we can point out the following phrases: «launching pad» in its terminological meaning is «стартовая площадка», in its transferred meaning - «отправной пункт», «to link up» - «стыков как омических кораблей, соединение», in its transformed meaning it means - «знакомиться»;
- b) a large group of phraseological units was formed from free word groups by transforming their meaning, e.g. «granny farm» - «пансионат для старых людей», «Trojan horse»

c) phraseological units can be formed by means of alliteration , e.g. «a sad sack» - «несчастный случай», «culture vulture» - « человек интересующийся искусством», «fudge and nudge» - «уклончивость ».

d) they can be formed by means of expressiveness, especially it is characteristic for forming interjections, e.g. «My aunt!», « Hear, hear !» etc

e) they can be formed by means of distorting a word group, e.g. «odds and ends» was formed from «odd ends»,

f) they can be formed by using archaisms, e.g. «in brown study» means «in gloomy meditation» where both components preserve their archaic meanings, g) they can be formed by using a sentence in a different sphere of life, e.g. «that cock won't fight» can be used as a free word-group when it is used in sports (cock fighting), it becomes a phraseological unit when it is used in everyday life, because it is used metaphorically,

h) they can be formed when we use some unreal image, e.g. «to have butterflies in the stomach» - «», «to have green fingers, etc. i) they can be formed by using expressions of writers or politicians in everyday life, e.g. «corridors of power» (Snow), «American dream» (Alby) «locust years» (Churchil), «the winds of change» (McMillan).[2]

An effective procedure of teaching English idioms for the students of non-philological universities should be based on sound theoretical and practical considerations. The procedure should combine two complementary parts: the general communication part and the academic communication part. The first one is to focus on the functional aspects of English idioms for general communication inside and outside the classroom. It provides the students with the necessary abilities to do things with language at the functional level: to interact socially, to explain, to argue, to discuss, to give directions, to invite, to express opinions on general topics, and so on.

The second part is to focus on providing students with specific professional idioms to enable them to comprehend authentic scientific texts in their relevant field of study, to summarize, to write scientific reports, to make notes from lectures, to discuss scientific concepts and to argue academically in their relevant field of specialization. To teach English idioms effectively the lesson should be designed with a special focus on business English vocabulary as the distinguishing component between General English and English. Activities can be compiled to offer students idioms in a context of a written text or dialogue which dealt with a specific topic (for example, banking). Exercises may traditionally comprise comprehension questions about the text and idioms drills. But such activities do not take into consideration the students' background, their previous knowledge, nor do they take into account how the learner might use these new idioms and idiomatic expressions in real-life situations. That is why we recommend putting a greater emphasis on the use of the new idioms in speaking, writing, listening, and reading within context. When students learn idioms and know how to use them in a professional context, their language functionality enlarges – they will get to know how to use language to recommend, advertise, or give advice (about some goods, services), clearly express opinions, or showing agreement and disagreement (during negotiations, discussions, meetings, councils), persuade, etc. Idioms perfectly suit the language of presentations, improving negotiating, or meeting skills.

Teaching idioms may become an amazing and useful process if some general rules specific for these specialties will be followed:

- 1) When introducing new idioms, teachers should keep limits, and not overwhelm students by throwing lists of phrases at them. Even if these idioms seem to be easy to understand and common, because students of non-linguistic universities are not going to remember a few dozen idiomatic expressions from one lesson. Instead, introduce a few idioms at a time. It can also help to keep them all related to a certain theme. For example, focus one lesson on a few animal-related idioms that can be

used during the interview (“work like a dog”, “dog days”, "the cat is out of the bag" etc.)

2) An effective method to teach English idioms is to use thematic derivations. For example, a teacher can use all sport-related idioms that can be used to discuss the contest between two companies. The use of thematic derivations makes it easier for students to grasp the meanings of the phrases, and see how similar words can mean very different things.

3) Introducing idioms through conversation is a very fruitful method. It can easily combine the process of learning English idioms with discussion on special themes giving students an idea of how the newly introduced idioms can be used in their professional activity. It's also a good exercise for inferring the meaning of an unfamiliar idiom based on context.

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